

2.2. COREQ List

In this epigraph we are going to answer the questions that compose COREQ list. The aim of this list is to write a report about the qualitative investigation. The investigation that made the interviews was the IP of the project *Historias de abandono*. Biographical-narrative approach to academic dropout in Andalusian universities. Multi-causal analysis and prevention proposals. Reference: B-SEJ-516-UGR18. Funding entity: FEDER Fund. The interviewer was a male professor (PhD) of the didactic department with more than twenty years of experience in the education field, working for the faculty of Education Sciences of Granada specialized in qualitative methods of investigation.

Before starting the interviews, the investigator made a couple of appointments with the sample with the purpose of creating links of sympathy. Just at the beginning of the real interview, the investigator makes an informed consent where he explained the aim of the investigation highlighting the educational objective of the interview.

As we explained in headlines before, it is a biographical-narrative investigation. The sample corresponds to different Andalusian universities: Jaen, Granada and Cadiz. A total of 21 participants, age ranged from 18 to 24 years old. Regarding gender, the sample included 14 men 7 women, distributed as follows: 1 from Cádiz, 7 from Granada and 14 from Jaen.

To conduct the interviews, a combined approach involving two sampling techniques was adopted. On one hand, voluntary convenience sampling was used to engage students who were willing to share their personal experiences and insights about university dropout, based on their own withdrawal from academic programs. The voluntary nature of this method fostered a trusting environment and elicited more in-depth responses, which were essential for qualitative analysis.

On the other hand, non-probabilistic snowball sampling was employed to expand the participant pool. Beginning with an initial set of students who had faced academic difficulties or were at risk of dropping out, these individuals referred to others in similar situations. This method proved particularly effective in accessing a population that is often difficult to reach directly. The way of collecting information was making an appointment in each university and travelling there, spending a couple of days in the university and making the interview face to face, using classrooms of each university for more privacy. During the interview there were only two people there: the interviewee and the investigator.

The instrument used for data collection was an interview with a semi-structured question protocol, organized into 10 dimensions: Background (3); School history in Preschool and Primary education (7); School history in Compulsory Secondary Education, Vocational Training, Baccalaureate, and other programs (5); Guidance received and the decision to access university (7); Work and pre-professional experiences (4); Academic experience during university studies (5); Causes of dropping out (5); Personal and work trajectory after dropping out (2); Academic trajectory after dropping out (2); Suggestions and advice (2), totaling 42 questions. For this research, the focus will be specifically on the "Causes of Dropping Out" dimension, which consists of 5 questions. No field notes were taken. The investigator used the recording software of his mobile phone. The duration of each interview was between 15 minutes to 60, depending on the story life of the interviewee. Data collection was considered complete when theoretical saturation was reached, that is, when no new relevant themes emerged.

When the audios were transcript, they were sent to the interviewees to correct if there was any mistake in the transcription.

Then we made a table of truth (see Table 1) with the codifications of each one of the interviews. After we used AQUAD v.8 to make a logical minimization to see the principal implicants.

2.3. Research quality criteria

To ensure the integrity of the data collected and the conclusions drawn from their analysis, using Guba and Lincoln (1989), we considered four criteria applied to qualitative research: credibility, transferability, reliability, and confirmability, and implemented various strategies to achieve them.

For the credibility or reliability offered by the results, we considered low-inference descriptors, since we used MP4 recordings. We also used member checking, given that the research conclusions were made available to the participants in the study. In this regard, the interviewees themselves provided feedback on the transcripts and confirmed that what was written was indeed correct and free of errors.

The use of triangulation is also planned, since the same purpose of this work will be addressed through an eminently quantitative design and typology using a causal approach based on Artificial Neural Network Analysis, with the ultimate goal of comparing qualitative and quantitative pathways.

For transferability or generalizability to similar contexts (case to case), we have used theoretical sampling (see the sampling process section).

For dependency or the possibility of replicating the study and obtaining similar results, we have used the establishment of review trails, since we record how the data were collected, how the participants were selected, etc.

Finally, for confirmability or to ensure that the research results are not biased by filters imposed by the researcher, we have proposed a confirmability audit by comparing our categorization processes with an external expert on university dropouts (agreement), as well as the low-level inference descriptors (recordings in MP4 format). Regarding the categorization processes of the 10 categories of analysis between the researcher and the external expert, we randomly selected (out of 10 interviews) the interview with participant 1. To this end, we calculated the agreement between the two using Cohen's Kappa coefficient. The results are as follows.

Table 1.

Cohen's Kappa coefficient

<i>Interview</i>	<i>Category</i>	<i>Agreement %</i>	<i>Kappa</i>	<i>z</i>	<i>p-value</i>
1	AANT	84%	0.48	2.27	.023*
1	BRPI	81%	0.41	2.35	.019*
1	CSEC	90%	0.78	3.69	<.001***
1	DORI	86%	0.50	2.66	.008**
1	ELAB	81%	0.55	2.83	.005**
1	FACA	86%	0.70	3.24	.001**
1	GCAB	81%	0.61	3.04	.002**
1	HPER	86%	0.66	3.07	.002**
1	IFOR	86%	0.67	3.27	.001**
1	JCON	87%	0.69	3.69	<.001***

Note: Significance: * $p < .05$; ** $p < .01$; $p < .001$

Meaning of categories:

University background (AANT).

Primary Education Success (BPRI).

Secondary Education Success (CSEC).
Good orientation (DORI).
Positive work experiences (ELAB).
Positive academic experiences (FACA).
Recognition of many causes of dropping out (GCAB).
Satisfactory personal career (HPER).
Successful educational career (IFOR).

As can be deduced from the results obtained in the table immediately above, with Landis & Koch (1977), Cohen's Kappa agreement coefficients have been diverse and range from values of 0.41 (fair) to 0.78 (substantial). However, the most important thing is that in all cases, they have all been statistically significant, at least, at a probability $p < 0.05$ and, therefore, they are statistically significant agreements that are not due to chance. In short, we can conclude that the researcher's categorization processes have been largely confirmed by an external evaluator expert in the subject under study.